

Experimental Investigations of the Rotational Stiffness of Single-Sided Fillet Welds

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ABSTRACT

Current design codes do not include a design approach for single-sided fillet welds subjected to bending. For this reason, and the expectations on the low bending resistance of single-sided fillet welds, fillet welds are generally welded from two sides. However, this is not always possible. Due to the geometric constraint of non-accessible hollow boxes, longitudinal fillet welds cannot be executed from two sides. This type of cross-section is often used in steel and steel-composite bridges with short and medium spans. It was found that these welds are subjected to bending caused by internal pressure fluctuations. This bending load is considered in the German National Design Regulation. The regulation was developed by simplified assumptions leading to an increase of the weld thickness of single-sided fillet welds. In this study, investigations regarding the bending behaviour of single-sided fillet welds are carried out. Therefore, specimens with single-sided fillet welds are subjected to a bending load. The results are compared to simplified analytical load-bearing capacities. It was found that the load bearing capacity of single-sided fillet welds is underestimated by the simplified calculation methods. The German regulation's increase of the weld thickness of single-sided fillet welds results in an uneconomical design of the welds.

Keywords: welds, single-sided fillet weld, small-sized box girder, bending

1 INTRODUCTION

Fillet welds are widely used in structural and mechanical engineering sectors due to their economic benefits. Compared to other types of welding, fillet welds are relatively simple to execute and do not require any weld preparation. The welds design is regulated by design code EN 1993 1-8 (1). According to this design code, fillet welds should always be welded from two sides. Figure 1 shows that welding from two sides allows bending loads in the weld, to carry the load as a pair of normal forces. This avoids weld bending and leads to compression stresses in one weld and tension stresses in the other. In the case of single-sided fillet welds, a bending load leads to unfavourable bending stresses in the fillet welds.

In some cases, welds cannot be welded from two sides, resulting in single-sided fillet welds. This happens on bridges with inaccessible hollow sections. These hollow sections are often used for short and medium span steel and steel-composite bridges. In Germany, inaccessible girders must be airtight. If the internal air temperature changes, the internal pressure fluctuates (2, 3). This causes bending in the longitudinal fillet welds. This load bends unfavourably the single-sided fillet welds of such girders (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Bending load on two-sided fillet welds and on one-sided fillet welds

When double-sided fillet welds cannot be executed, the bending stress of single-sided fillet welds must be considered in the bearing capacity check. The current standard EN 1993-1-8 (1) does not provide any information regarding the bending in single-sided fillet welds. The draft Eurocode prEN 1993-1-8:2021 (4) recommends using elastic design rules, such as the directional method for design check.

Pressure variations occur inside inaccessible airtight welded box girders, which lead to a bending load in the single-sided fillet welds. A design rule for single-sided fillet welds has been developed in (3) to account for bending stresses due to this pressure variation. Therefore, an elastic analysis of the theoretical bending resistance, based on the simplified method of EN 1993 1-8 was carried out. Depending on the longitudinal shear utilisation (3) proposed to increase the weld thickness and set minimum values. This requirement has been included in the National Bridge Guideline (5).

This paper investigates the load-bearing capacity of single-sided fillet welds subjected to bending loads. These tests were part of the research project "Economic dimensioning of fillet welds of airtight welded box girders".

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS ON SINGLE-SIDED FILLET WELDS

2.1 Setup

To investigate the strength of single-sided fillet welds, two 690 mm long and 20 mm thick plates were welded together. The manual welding process used is MAG welding. Stiffeners were previously welded to maintain perpendicularity between the plates. Subsequently, three test specimens of 150 mm length were cut from each of the 690 mm long welded sheets (Fig. 2). Welding was carried out at nominal thicknesses of 5 mm, 7 mm and 10 mm. The base material consists of S355 JR steel grade, and the used filler material corresponds to strength class 46.

Fig. 2. Test specimen before cutting

The specimens were attached to a console which was mounted on the rigid base of a Zwick 600 universal testing machine. Eccentricity between the test cylinder and the weld is created, leading to a bending load while loading the specimens. The test arrangement is shown in Figure 3. The tests were

performed under displacement control. By an inclinometer, the rotation of the plate was measured. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was further used to measure the strain field on the weld.

Fig. 3. Test setup

2.2 Test results

In this paper, a total of 9 specimens with 3 different weld thickness were analysed. The following graph shows the moment-rotation curves obtained from the tests. The acting moment is obtained by multiplying the load by the lever arm and normalized to the length of the weld per centimeter.

Fig. 4. Moment versus rotational plot the single-sided fillet welds

It was found that an increasing weld thickness leads to an increasing of the load-bearing capacity and the rotation. For welds with a nominal thickness of 5 mm, the maximum resistance is 120 Nm/cm. The load-bearing capacity doubles for welds with a nominal thickness of 7mm. Here, the maximum load bearing capacity is 290 Nm/cm. The resistance increases to over 400 Nm/cm at the nominal thickness of 10 mm. This non-linear increase in the maximum load-bearing capacity between the tests can be explained by the aid of the real thickness, which considers the weld penetration. To determine the real weld thickness microsections of the welds were made. The weld thickness was measured using a microscope, shown in Figure 5. It was found that the real weld thickness is significantly greater than the nominal weld thickness.

Fig. 5. Microsection to determinate the real weld thickness

2.3 Comparison between experimental and analytical load-bearing capacity according to EC 3

In the following the experimental results are compared with the analytical load-bearing capacity of single sided fillet welds under bending. For this reason, the directional method of EN 1993-1-8 is used. The acting stresses are determined by the beam theory, assuming an elastic and a plastic stress distribution. The design check according to EN 1993-1-8 using the directional method shall satisfy the following two criteria:

$$\sqrt{\sigma_{\perp}^2 + 3(\tau_{\perp}^2 + \tau_{\parallel}^2)} \leq \frac{f_u}{\beta_w \gamma_{M2}} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{\perp} \leq \frac{0.9f_u}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (2)$$

Equation 1 checks, whether an interaction of shear and normal forces exceeds the limit stress. The limit stress is derived from the tensile strength f_u of the base material. The correlation factor β_w accounts for the overmatching of the filler material to the base material, resulting in an increased load-bearing capacity of the weld (5), (6). For steels of greater grade than S460, the draft prEN 1993-1-8:2021 provides a variation of equation 1. In this case, the limit stress calculation accounts for the strength of the filler material. The normal stresses are checked using equation 2. Here, the resistance is reduced by a factor of 0.9. This criterion is not decisive, as shear and normal stresses in the weld usually occur in combination. In the case of pure bending, this criterion is decisive since the following applies:

$$\frac{0.9f_u}{\gamma_{M2}} \leq \frac{f_u}{\beta_w \gamma_{M2}} \quad (3)$$

As referred in EN 1993-1-8, the stress distribution is calculated according to the elastic beam theory. The limit stress is taken from equation (2). It is considered inconsistent in the design process to use ultimate strength for elastic analysis, because the elastic stress distribution under bending does not attain the tensile strength. For this reason, the elastic load-bearing capacity is calculated, for comparison, using the yield stress f_y . The following equations are used to calculate the maximum analytical values of elastic and plastic resistance under bending. The partial safety factor γ_{M2} is set to 1.0. The reduction factor of 0.9, as defined in equation (2), is not utilized for comparison purposes.

$$M_{el,th} = f_y \cdot W_{el} = f_y \cdot \frac{a_w^2 \cdot l_w}{6} \quad (4)$$

$$M_{pl,th} = f_u \cdot W_{pl} = f_u \cdot \frac{a_w^2 \cdot l_w}{4} \quad (5)$$

The maximum plastic load capacity $M_{pl,exp}$ has been analysed for each test and corresponds to the maximum bending load achieved in the test. According to the beam theory, a shape coefficient α can be determined for each cross-section to determine the ratio between the elastic moment M_{el} and the plastic moment M_{pl} :

$$\alpha = \frac{W_{pl}}{W_{el}} \quad (6)$$

For square sections, the shape coefficient is $\alpha=1.5$. The shape coefficient allows to evaluate the experimental elastic moment, which is calculated as follows:

$$M_{el,exp} = \frac{M_{max,exp}}{1.5} \quad (7)$$

Figure 6 compares the theoretical resistance with the test results as a function of weld thickness. The experimental data is not related to the nominal weld thickness, but to the measured weld thickness.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the calculated load-bearing capacity with the experimental load-bearing capacity

Under consideration of the elastic and plastic bending resistance, the plot shows that the load-bearing capacity is underestimated. On the other hand, the load-bearing capacity of the welds increases linearly with the weld thickness. This contrasts with the beam theory, according to which resistance increases with the square of the weld thickness.

3 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

According to the beam theory, the experimental load-bearing capacity is much higher than the analytical calculation. For comparison purposes, the maximal load-bearing capacity under bending is calculated according to Eurocode:

$$M_{Rk,EC-3} = 0.9 \cdot f_u \cdot W_{el} \quad (8)$$

The left sub-figure of Figure 7 compares the experimental load-bearing capacity $M_{pl,exp}$ to the calculated load-bearing capacity $M_{Rk,EC-3}$. If the load-bearing capacity was well approximated by the analytical calculation, the experimental data would correlate with the bisector. However, the load-bearing capacity is underestimated. In the right sub-figure, the ratio between analytical and the experimental load-bearing capacity $M_{Rk,EC}/M_{Rk,exp}$ is shown. On the abscissa, the measured weld thickness is shown. It is evident that the analytical approach given by the Eurocode underestimates the experimental data by around 50%.

Fig. 7. Comparison of analytical calculation of the load-bearing capacity according to EC-3 and experimental data

In summary, the national regulation (RE-ING) underestimates the load-bearing capacity of single-sided fillet welds under bending. This leads to an uneconomical execution of welds in small-sized box girders. Effects of the filler material and the steel grades of the base material on the load-bearing capacity must be investigated furthermore. Additional tests, to investigate the behaviour of single-sided fillet welds under combined shear and bending load, have to be carried out. Numerical investigations and DIC measurements are essential to comprehend the stress-strain distribution and to develop an appropriate analytical model.

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REFERENCES

1. DIN Standards Committee Building and Civil Engineering. EN 1993-1-8 (2005) Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-8: Design of joints
2. LTAIEF, Malik and Martin Mensinger. Fillet welds of airtight welded hollow boxes. *Stahlbau*. 2023 Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/stab.202300044>
3. RADTKE, Frank K. F. and Ralf Schubart. Contribution to the design approach of welds in airtight box girders under temperature induced internal pressure. *Stahlbau* 2019 Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/stab.201900084>
4. DIN Standards Committee Building and Civil Engineering. prEN 1993-1-8:2021 (E) Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-8: Design of joints, Draft

5. SNIJDER, H. H., et al. Evaluation of Test Results on Welded Connections in order to obtain Strength Functions and Suitable Model Factors. Part A: Results. Eurocode 3. 1988.
6. SNIJDER, H. H., et al. Evaluation of Test Results on Welded Connections in order to obtain Strength Functions and Suitable Model Factors Part B: Evaluations. Eurocode 3. 1988.
7. BMVI, Guidelines for the design, construction and equipment of civil structures – RE-ING. 2019